

Characterisation of key aroma compounds in foods containing vegetable proteins

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Abstract

The aroma profile of foods containing vegetable proteins is complex due to the presence of a large number of compounds belonging to different chemical classes. The manufacturing process use many parameters of which temperature plays a role in the generation of volatile compounds. The flavour profiles of two vegetable proteins samples (high and low thermal processing) were studied. GC-MS analyses detected and identified 71 aroma compounds (pyrazines, alcohols, ketones, aldehydes) in the two samples. Quantification showed a difference between the two thermal treatments. GC-O analysis described 70 olfactive areas, 39 of which attributed to a chemical compound.

Keywords: Vegetable proteins, Food, SAFE, GC-O, GC-MS

Introduction

For several years, vegetable proteins have been the subject of particular attention. Considered by many people as the food of the future, they are more and more popular within consumers.

The project GenVie aimed to develop new foods based on vegetable protein in order to obtain a good digestibility and acceptability by the consumer [1, 2]. To better characterize the taste of these products, we conducted experiments to identify the flavour compounds in two samples produced at different thermal processes. The two vegetable protein samples (high and low thermal processing) [3] were submitted in triplicate to Solvent Assisted Flavour Evaporation (SAFE) [4]. The aroma compounds present in the resulting aqueous distillate were extracted with dichloromethane. The identification and quantification of the aroma compounds were performed by Gas Chromatography–Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS). The odorant compounds were detected by Gas Chromatography–Olfactometry (GC-O) with a panel of ten assessors.

Experimental

The manufacture of vegetable meats consists of producing protein fibres from an extract of concentrate and giving them a structure similar to that of meat. Depending on the product, the addition of flavour, fats, colourings, nutritional additives and coagulable proteins is possible. The two vegetable proteins samples (high-GV1 and low-GV3 thermal processing) studied are developed and produced by Tereos, they contain about 50 to 70% water.

Extraction of volatile compounds (Solvent Assisted Flavour Evaporation)

Each vegetable proteins sample (50 g) was crushed and mixed with 60 ml of ultra-pure water. Three hundred microliters of butan-1-ol solution (124 ng/μl in water) were added for internal standardisation. This mixture was stirred, introduced into the SAFE apparatus and vacuum distillation was performed for two hours. The thermostat of the head and legs of the apparatus was fixed at 37°C. The same temperature was used to heat the distillation vessel by means of a water bath. The aqueous distillate was then extracted with dichloromethane (1 x 20 ml then 2 x 10 ml). After liquid-liquid separation, the organic phase was collected and filtered through glass wool and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The extract was concentrated to 400 μl with a Kuderna-Danish apparatus in a 70°C water bath.

Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS)

GC-MS analyses were performed using a 7890A series GC-5975C quadrupole MSD (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, USA) equipped with a DB-WAX column (30 m length x 0.32 mm i.d., 0.5 μm film thickness; Agilent J&W). One microliter of each extract was injected in splitless mode. The oven temperature was held at 40°C, raised to 240°C at 4°C/min and then held at 240°C for 10 min. Helium, as the carrier gas, was run at a constant flow rate of 1.5 ml/min. (velocity 44 cm/s). The injector and detector transfer line temperatures were both maintained at 250°C. Mass spectra were obtained in the electron ionisation mode with an energy voltage of 70eV. Acquisitions were achieved in scan mode (mass range m/z 29-350 uma, 4 scans/s).

The compounds were identified based on their retention indices (RIs) and mass spectra. RI values were calculated using the Van den Dool and Kratz formula from the retention times of *n*-alkanes (C₁₀-C₃₀) on the same column. RI values were compared with RIs from the literature. The mass spectra were compared with those from databases: NIST, WILEY and INRAMASS (internal database achieved using standard compounds).

Gas Chromatography-Olfactometry (GC-O)

GC-O analyses were performed using an HP 6890A GC (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, USA) coupled to a flame ionisation detector (FID) and an olfactometric detection port (ODP, Gerstel sniffing, Gerstel Mülheim an der Ruhr, Germany). This system was used with a DB-Wax column, (30 m length x 0.32 mm i.d 0.5 µm film thickness; Agilent J&W). The chromatographic conditions were the same as for GC-MS analysis. The column was equipped with a Y-splitter dividing effluent between the FID and the ODP (ratio1:1). Each analysis was carried out with a panel of ten assessors, a total 10 analyses per extract. During a 40 min analysis, the assessors were asked to describe the odour perceived using their own words. Odour descriptions and times were recorded using Olfactory Recorder software (Gerstel). The data were processed using the detection frequency method. Odorant zones (OZ) were characterised by the number of assessors detecting an odour active compound at the ODP simultaneously (detection frequency, odour descriptions by the whole panel and the retention index on the DB-Wax column). One OZ was taken into consideration if the detection frequency was higher than 4/10 (40%) for at least one extract.

Results and discussion

The combination of GC-MS and GC-O analysis provided the identification of volatile compounds and the odour associated with some of them (Table 1). Seventy-four volatile compounds were identified and semi-quantified with the internal standard (butan-1-ol). Seventy odorant zones (OZ) were selected four or more times in at least one sample and thirty-nine OZ were attributed to a chemical compound.

We observe that the amounts of pyrazines (written in orange) and ketones (written in purple) are more intense in GV1 sample (High thermal processing) than in GV3 sample (Low thermal processing). In contrast, the amounts of alcohols (written in green) decreased in GV1 compared to GV3.

For pyrazines classes, the detection frequency is greater in GV1 in accordance with the quantity. The odour description were noted as grilled, peanuts, earth, and cabbage.

Most of the aldehydes (written in blue) are detected by the panel with two categories of descriptors: vegetable, fruity, floral for the saturated aldehydes and grilled, cereals, spicy, popcorn, and oil for the unsaturated ones. Only some ketones and alcohols have been described as fruity, floral, solvent, and chemical.

The compounds oct-1-en-3-one (11), oct-1-en-3-ol (26), and furaneol (69) were detected in GCO analysis but they were not detected in GC-MS analysis. The identification was based on odour descriptors and on retention indices (experimental and literature).

Table 1: Identification of volatile compounds by GCMS and associated odours by GCO

Peak Number	Compounds Identification	Retention Index		Standard Equivalent Concentration (µg/kg)		Odour Description
		RI _{Exp}	RI _{Litt}	GV1	GV3	Detection frequency (/10) [GV1/GV3]
1	Hexanal	1080	1078	1275	2465	cut grass, vegetable [7/8]
2	Heptan-2-one	1180	1184	237	151	fruity, sweet [3/4]
3	Heptanal	1183	1185	176	135	
4	Limonene	1198	1189	91	107	
5	2-pentylfuran	1230	1230	718	615	
6	Pentan-1-ol	1249	1251	137	543	
7	2-methylpyrazine	1262	1264	120	22	
8	3-hydroxybutan-2-one	1278	1280	107	215	
9	Octan-2-one	1283	1287	66	41	
10	Octanal	1286	1289	128	104	lemon, fruity, citrus [5/6]
11	Oct-1-en-3-one	1304	1298	nd	nd	mushroom [10/8]
12	1-hydroxypropan-2-one	1292	1290	232	53	
13	2,5-dimethylpyrazine	1320	1323	497	336	
14	2,6-dimethylpyrazine	1326	1328	205	88	

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15	Ethylpyrazine	1331	1333	19	trace	grilled, toast, peanuts [9/4]
16	6-methylhept-5-en-2-one	1334	1339	13	trace	
17	Hexan-1-ol	1352	1352	340	3000	
18	2-ethyl-6-methylpyrazine	1383	1385	59	20	rotten, gas, cabbage [9/8]
19	Nonan-2-one	1386	1390	40	23	
20	Nonanal	1390	1392	376	266	fruity, candy [4/0]
21	Trimethylpyrazine	1402	1406	230	77	mushroom [8/5]
22	Oct-3-en-2-one	1403	1414	trace	trace	spicy, burnt, dust [6/3]
23	5-ethylformylcyclopent-1-ene	1412	-	103	103	
24	(E)-Oct-2-enal	1425	1437	116	129	wine stopper, chemical [9/7]
25	3-ethyl-2,5-dimethylpyrazine	1443	1447	131	49	asparagus, earth, potato [8/6]
26	Oct-1-en-3-ol	1450	1456	nd	nd	vegetal, earth, cardboard [7/3]
27	Methional (ion 104)	1447	1443	6,2E+04	1,4E+04	potato [9/8]
28	Oct-1-en-3-ol	1448	1451	229	400	
29	Furfural	1454	1460	241	73	
30	Heptan-1-ol (ion 70)	1454	1453	1,3E+05	6,5E+05	
31	2-ethyl-3,5-dimethylpyrazine	1460	1460	65	9	dust, earth, vegetable [7/3]
32	2-ethylhexan-1-ol (ion 57)	1488	1484	3,2E+05	3,3E+05	
33	Decan-2-one (ion 58)	1490	1489	3,4E+05	1,6E+05	floral, vegetal [7/3]
34	Decanal (ion 112)	1495	1495	2,9E+05	1,0E+05	floral, vegetal [7/6]
35	Acetylfurane (ion 95)	1499	1501	1,4E+06	3,2E+05	
36	Non-3-en-2-one	1507	1506	29	27	
37	Benzaldehyde	1514	1528	480	362	
38	(E)-Non-2-enal	1530	1532	104	79	dust, mothballs, cardboard [10/8]
39	Octan-1-ol	1556	1550	104	148	
40	Undecan-3-one	1561	1555	58	48	
41	5-methyl-2-furfural (ion 110)	1564	1567	1,1E+05	4,0E+04	
42	2-pentylpyridine	1573	1572	69	27	anise, mint [10/7]
43	β -caryophyllene (ion 93)	1594	1597	8,2E+04	1,0E+05	
44	Undecan-2-one (ion 58)	1594	1598	2,0E+05	1,5E+05	
45	Butyrolactone	1615	1617	196	78	toasted, hazelnut, burnt [10/5]
46	6-Dodecanone	1625	-	57	46	floral, animal [8/3]
47	Phenylacetaldehyde (ion 91)	1633	1648	6,6E+05	3,1E+05	
48	2-acetylthiazole	1638	1644	62	77	grilled, hazelnut, popcorn [5/7]
49	2-Furanmethanol	1653	1659	704	178	
50	(E,Z)-Nona-2,4-dienal	1659	1650	trace	trace	grilled, popcorn, cooked rice [10/5]
51	6(5)-methyl-2-acetylpyrazine	1674	-	29	trace	
52	γ -hexalactone	1690	1694	39	49	
53	(E,E)-Nona-2,4-dienal	1693	1702	27	49	grilled, cereals, spicy [10/8]
54	4-ethylbenzaldehyde (ion 134)	1698	1752	5,7E+04	1,0E+05	anise, fruity, mint [8/7]
55	Δ -Carvone	1727	1728	73	120	
56	2(5H)-Furanone	1739	1745	265	90	plant, bug [8/5]
57	Undecen-2-al	1746	1755	217	154	grilled, hazelnut, popcorn [8/6]
58	(E,Z)-deca-2,4-dienal	1757	1753	353	388	oil, grilled, vegetable [8/6]
59	(E,E)-deca-2,4-dienal	1807	1805	3281	2856	oil, spice, burnt, toasted [9/5]

60	3-methyl-6-propylphenol	1836	-	265	486	
61	Benzyl alcohol	1867	1867	150	215	pharmacy, synthol, solvent, clove, chemical [10/6]
62	2-phenylethanol (ion 91)	1902	1902	7,3E+05	1,6E+06	floral, solvent, coconut [10/7]
63	2-acetylpyrrole	1960	1952	104	21	
64	Maltol (ion 126)	1961	1931	7,1E+06	1,5E+06	sweet, vanilla, caramel [7/3]
65	Phenol (ion 94)	1994	-	2,6E+05	2,0E+05	paint, metallic, vegetal [9/7]
66	2-formylpyrrole	2011	2009	101	trace	floral, vegetal, anise, pepper, vanilla, gingerbread [5/5]
67	γ -nonalactone	2017	2023	288	361	coconut, fruity, sweet [7/7]
68	Octadecanal	2022	2020	116	163	
69	Furaneol	2033	2033	nd	nd	cotton candy, caramel, vanilla [8/4]
70	5-pentyl-5(H)-furan-2-one	2063	-	192	170	sweet, vanilla, coconut, woody, pine, vegetal [7/6]
71	2-phenoxyethanol	2131	2139	127	64	sweet, fruity, lactone [7/5]
72	Caprolactam	2173	-	353	194	
73	2-methoxy-4-vinylphenol	2182	2181	61	28	Spices, chorizo, cabbage [9/3]
74	Indole	2428	2435	83	33	

RI Exp: experimental retention indices on DB-Wax column. RI Litt: literature retention indices on DB-Wax column

Text in grey: volatile compounds coelution. Ion specific area

n.d: not detected by GC-MS

Trace: not quantified

Conclusion

The results of this study constitute a first step in the knowledge of volatile compounds in foods made with vegetable proteins. GC-MS and GC-O data showed a large spectrum of identified compounds (pyrazines, alcohols, ketones, aldehydes) and associated descriptors (roasted, vegetal, fruity...) contributing to the richness and complexity of the sample flavours. The chromatographic profile of the two samples is the same while the quantities of compounds are different between the two thermal treatments. The amounts of pyrazines and ketones are higher in GV1 sample (high temperature) while the amounts of alcohols are higher in sample GV3 (low temperature).

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